

Prediction of Sudden Cardiac Death among Malaysians

Ramalan Kematian Kardium Tiba-tiba dalam Kalangan Rakyat Malaysia

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ABSTRACT

Sudden cardiac death is also known as SCD, which is a natural death caused by failure of the heart function. It is different from heart attack as SCD does not cause injuries to the victims. Researchers have developed many devices using heart rate variability (HRV) to predict SCD but the best technique is still yet to be discovered. HRV is said to be the potential predictors for SCD. In this paper, two types of peak detectors are evaluated to measure which one is the most robust. Firstly, visual inspection of electrocardiogram (ECG) is carried out by observing the P wave, QRS complex, R peak, T wave, ST segment and also some abnormalities in ECG, where initial interpretation can be made. 62 recordings of 10 seconds ECG from a single patient are combined to view the overall ECG waveform. An algorithm is developed to clean the ECG and to detect R peak. From the results, it is found that 'QRS_detect2' function is a better peak detector as it demonstrates more accurate and precise marks on every R peak. As a conclusion, prediction of SCD can be performed using HRV with 'QRS_detect2' as the R peak detectors.

Keywords: Sudden cardiac death; electrocardiogram; heart rate variability; e-Health sensor; Arduino.

ABSTRAK

Kematian kardium tiba-tiba merupakan kematian secara semulajadi yang terjadi disebabkan oleh kegagalan fungsi jantung. Kematian kardium tiba-tiba ialah berbeza dengan serangan jantung kerana kematian kardium tiba-tiba tidak menunjukkan sebarang kecederaan kepada mangsa. Kajian telah menghasilkan peranti yang menggunakan kebolehubahan kadar jantung untuk meramal kematian kardium tiba-tiba namun sehingga kini masih belum ditemukan dengan teknik yang terbaik. Kebolehubahan kadar jantung dilihat sebagai peramal yang berpotensi untuk meramal kematian kardium tiba-tiba. Dalam kertas kerja ini, dua jenis penanda puncak dikenal pasti bagi mengukur pengukur puncak yang terbaik di antara kedua-dua penanda puncak tersebut. Eksperimen secara visual terhadap EKG dilakukan bagi mengesan bentuk gelombang P, kompleks QRS, puncak R, segmen ST dan juga beberapa ketidaknormalan EKG. Sejumlah 62 rakaman bagi EKG selama 10 saat oleh seorang pesakit. Sebuah algoritma dibangunkan untuk memproses data EKG dan beberapa penanda puncak turut dikenal pasti dan diuji. Berdasarkan keputusan yang diperolehi, 'QRS-detect2' merupakan penanda puncak yang terbaik kerana ia dapat menanda kesemua puncak R. Sebagai konklusi, ramalan kematian kardium tiba-tiba boleh dilakukan dengan menggunakan kebolehubahan kadar jantung dengan 'QRS_detect2' sebagai penanda puncak R.

Kata kunci: Kematian kardium tiba-tiba; elektrokardiogram; kebolehubahan kadar jantung; pengesan e-Health; Arduino

INTRODUCTION

A lot of researches had been done but there is no findings regarding suitable techniques to predict sudden cardiac death (SCD) (Murukesan et al. 2013). Although normal ECG reading from a patient that has high potential to experience SCD

does not shown any significant difference, the signal of heart rate variability (HRV) can be used as the markers to predict SCD (Ebrahimzadeh et al. 2014). SCD is associated with the cause of coronary heart disease and the possibilities increase with the increasing age of a person (Theilade et al. 2013).

With the technology of measuring heart signal by using electrocardiogram (ECG), the machine plays a huge contribution in medical field. By using ECG, it is easier for the medical practitioners to observe the patient heart rather than by only using stethoscope that can only listen the heart beat. ECG morphology can determine a lot of possibilities that a person may or may not having heart problems. To understand the meaning of ECG waveforms, the person who in charge of reading the ECG signals must have a good knowledge on how to read ECG morphology correctly.

Figure 1: PQRST waveform and R-R interval (Source: <https://www.mythlete.com/blog-hrv-in-sports-training-1/r-r-interval-trace/>)

Figure 2: A human heart (Source: <https://fineartamerica.com/featured/gross-anatomy-of-the-human-heart-stocktrek-images.html>)

A single heart beat consist of atrial depolarization, ventricular depolarization and ventricular repolarization. ECG will shows the waveform of PQRST that signifies the heart beat. A normal resting heart beat per minute for adults is usually 60-100 bpm.

HRV is the change in the time intervals between adjacent heartbeat and it can varies when a person make a movement such as from resting state into running (McCarty & Shaffer 2015). When a person runs, the heart will do extra work as it need to pump more blood to supply oxygen to all parts of the body. Increasing physical activity will increase the heart rate. This is where the heart rate will varies from each other as it is not always the same. SCD victim may have lower HRV than individuals that are healthy (Mølgaard et al. 1991).

The R-R interval from one to another can vary according to people's activity. An experiment has shown significant findings that HRV signal can be

used for prediction of SCD though there is no difference between normal ECG and those who are prone to SCD (Ebrahimzadeh et al. 2014).

SCD is initiated by the problems of ventricular tachyarrhythmia such as ventricular tachycardia (VT), ventricular flutter (VFL) or ventricular fibrillation (VFib). Some cases of SCD may come from ventricular bradycardia but in only a small percentage (Shen T et al. 2016).

Prediction of SCD in view of HRV has its own particular confinement. To start with, HRV cannot be dependably evaluated in patients with atrial fibrillation (AF) or frequent premature ventricular contractions (PVC). These produces chance that high-hazard patients can be prohibited from treatment since HRV examination give wrong outcome. Next, HRV additionally affected by various factors, for example, age, sexual orientation and types of medication taken by patients (Murukesan et al. 2013).

METHODOLOGY

For this paper, it is important to know basic interpretation of ECG by doing visual inspection of ECG's morphology. ECG consists of PQRST waveform that shows the heart rate mechanism of human being. 12-lead ECG has huge contribution in medical field study especially in interpreting the possible heart condition of a patient. By visual experiment of the ECG waveform analysis, patients will be identified by the physician on their current heart condition. ECG is used in this paper to obtain the waveform output and the ECG format will be converted to a file that is compatible to be used in MATLAB. To enable the algorithm's function, the ECG data format that is in .xml need to be converted first. By using specified algorithm and library, the data can be converted thus making further analysis for preprocessing and signal processing of ECG waveform.

Next, 62 recordings of 10 seconds ECG from a single patient are combined. The recordings are concatenated vertically so that it can form a horizontal graph shape of 10 minutes ECG recordings. ECG data has 12 different leads that are three bipolar limb leads of lead I, II, III, six unipolar chest leads V1, V2, V3, V4, V5, V6 and three unipolar limb leads aVL, aVR, and aVF. This project is focusing on lead II ECG data as it gives a good view of P wave, and it is commonly used for rhythm strip. When the ECG file that is in .xml is converted to .mat files, MATLAB shows a table of 12 leads ECG data with their header name as the table title. To continue the process, the header must be removed as the header will give an error of data reading. The chosen data header of lead II will be deleted for further ECG algorithm analysis.

Before generating an algorithm that can detect the R peak of overall data, some signal processing need to be done as the data obtain from ECG is a raw data. Thus it need to go for removing the noise such as filtering the 50 Hz frequency and removing the baseline by using Fast Fourier Transform analysis. From the raw data of ECG, the graph will shows a wave-like structure that indicates the breathing pattern during the ECG recording.

After the filtering process, an algorithm that can detect the R peak is then generated. A few peak detectors have been discovered and analysed of its accuracy. Some peak detectors does not give a good results as it marks the wrong peak. After doing some improvement and calculation that may possibly results in an accurate R peak detection, the waveform output shows significant findings of a processed ECG waveform and a peak detector. Based on R peaks obtained, it is a sign of ventricular depolarization. R-R peak interval can determine various heart condition. The simplest way to measure heart rate is by observing the R-R peak. Using peak detector algorithm, the heart rate per minute can be calculated from MATLAB without using pulse oximeter or by pressing the finger on vital points of a patient.

Furthermore, the R peak that is obtained in every peak the ECG waveform shown will be related to the HRV. The HRV may varies from one R-R interval to another R-R interval. According to Jason Moore, high variations means high HRV thus indicates a healthy heart condition.

After that, a method of obtaining ECG recording is made by using e-Health sensor. Six 23 years old, male and healthy subjects are chosen to further research in ECG hands-on operation. The ECG data collected will undergo same procedure of MATLAB file conversion of .xml to .mat file,

Figure 3: e-Health sensor and connection settings (Source: <https://www.cooking-hacks.com/documentation/tutorials/ehealth-v1-biometric-sensor-platform-arduino-raspberry-pi-medical/>)

filtering process by using the signal processing techniques, obtain peak detectors that can mark the R peak and relate the R peak with HRV.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the methodology explained, the visual inspection of ECG signals is completed. It is important to be able to read the ECG waveform as it is the fundamental study before beginning the project. Learning ECG morphology is crucial as through visual inspection, the PQRS waveform, the R peak, the ST segment, QRS complex and other ECG morphology can be easily understood. Some interpretation regarding possible heart condition can be made by reading the ECG waveform results in the patient's data. After visual inspection of ECG signals, the signals will be inserted to MATLAB and the converted files are successfully converted and are used for further processing approach.

Figure 4: 62 recordings of 10 seconds ECG from a single patient are combined

Figure 5: 'QRS_detect2' peak detector (Behar et al. 2013)

Figure 6: 'Findpeaks' peak detector

Figure 7: HRV of 62 recording of 10 seconds ECG signals

Next, the results of 62 recordings of 10 seconds ECG from a single patient is obtained and shown in Fig. 4. A graph of 300 seconds ECG recording is successfully tabulated and the tabulated data is inserted to a graph for easier and readable visual output. The graph may look saturated as the 10 minutes ECG recording has more than total number of 600 heart beats. A clearer graph can be obtained by limiting the x-axis time value. For example, the 10 minutes ECG recording shows an x-axis table of 600 seconds time and the graph will be zoomed in until 5 minutes of ECG data recording that is 300 seconds.

The raw ECG data recording will be filtered to remove a 50 Hz frequency noise so that the graph will have a smooth data. The filtering

process of using Fast Fourier Transform will have a baseline removal, hence a clearer image for better processing. When the filtering process is finished, the R peak detector algorithm is made and compared. The results showed two peak detectors that are almost accurate as it can detect all R peak without leaving any R peak unmarked. Two peak detectors are named 'findpeaks' and 'QRS_detect2'. From comparison, the 'QRS_detect2' peak detector is a robust peak detector as it can detect the entire peak. These two peak detectors are not the only peak detectors that have been tested. The 'findpeaks' peak detector is obtained from MATLAB functions of findpeaks. The results are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6.

When recording the data from e-Health sensor, it is found that the results obtained are not the same as the actual ECG recording. According to e-Health tutorial itself, they have a step-by-step guidance from electrode connections until the Arduino program codes. However, it is unable to provide a good result as a normal ECG recording. This may be due to the hardware problems such as the Arduino UNO should be replaced with a new Arduino, or there is some error when uploading the file to Arduino although it shows no error and it is already uploaded to the Arduino. Other than that, it may seem like the electrodes are damaged so that when it is attached to the body, it is not sensitive and causing more noises at the output. The waveform output seen by inserting the data collected from Arduino serial monitor to MATLAB to generate the ECG graph. Hence the result obtained is not like the predicted outcomes.

Based on the results obtained, the peak detector of 'QRS_detect2' is the most accurate peak detector. It is tested with other recording and the results shown are positive, meaning that the peak detector 'QRS_detect2' can mark the peak of any ECG recording data of different subjects. This peak detector is compatible and can be used by other ECG data. The HRV can be measured by measuring the R peak of one side to the other side of the R peak which is the intervals between two R peaks. According to Oura Health Ltd. in Finland, the R-R intervals may vary with each other and this can result in variability of heart rate. SCD victims are said to have low HRV. Low HRV is indicated when the person's ECG data shows the constant R-R interval at every interval measure.

CONCLUSION

Based on the project that has been conducted, the visual inspection of ECG signals is completed as the basic knowledge of reading ECG signals and detecting the differences between P wave, QRS complex, R peak and ST segment is accomplished. The algorithm to build the peak detectors to detect the R peak is also successfully obtained in this project. Based on the peak detectors that have been built and tested in the subjects' ECG, the peak marked can measure the heart rate per minute and also to measure the HRV. 'QRS_detect2' is a robust peak detector as it can detect all the peaks in every ECG recording.

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